

CONSTITUENTS OF *CENTALLA ASIATICA*. PART III.
EXAMINATION OF THE INDIAN VARIETY

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The components of the Indian variety of the plant *Centalla asiatica* have been examined. The main triterpenic constituent, indocentoic acid, appears to be isomeric with centoic acid, isolated from the Ceylonese variety.

In previous communications of this series (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 579, 630; *Nature*, 1949, 163, 258, 260) the isolation of a triterpenoid glycoside and three polyhydroxy triterpenic acids- centic, centoic and centellic acids- from the Ceylonese variety of *Centalla asiatica* has been described and the structures of the triterpenes discussed. In the present communication the results of examination of the Indian variety of the plant have been recorded.

The constituents of the plants were like those of the Ceylonese variety. It was also found to contain salts, sugars, essential oils and pectin. The most characteristic constituent in this case also is, however, a mixture of triterpenic acids which can be isolated and initially purified by following exactly the same procedure as adopted for the Ceylonese variety. The ultimate aqueous mother-liquor, left after precipitation of the triterpenes, has been found to contain a considerable amount of a water-soluble glycoside which is also a sugar-ester, like centelloside and asiaticoside (vide Parts I and II, *loc. cit.*) and, like these, could be hydrolysed easily by both acid and alkali. The presence of sugar-ester type glycosides appears to be a characteristic for *C. asiatica*.

In the present case the individual triterpenic constituents were separated through the crystallisation of their brucine salts and were divided into three distinct and two unspecified minor fractions (vide Experimental). Of these, only the major triterpenic constituent, "indocentoic acid", and the water-soluble glycoside, "indocentelloside", were examined in some details.

The equivalent weight of indocentoic acid, as determined by micro-titrations, when correlated with elemental analysis, clearly indicates that like centoic acid, it has the same molecular formula $C_{30}H_{48}O_6$, which has been further confirmed by equivalent weight and analysis of the acetyl and other derivatives. It responds to the usual colour tests for triterpenes.

Indocentoic acid does not react with any carbonyl reagent and does not show any U. V. absorption. Like centoic acid, the carboxyl group in it is also tertiary, as the crystalline methyl ester, obtained through reaction with diazomethane, is resistant towards hydrolysis. The presence of a double bond was indicated by colour reaction with tetranitromethane, but, as expected, it was also resistant towards hydrogenation. Formation of bromolactone reveals the usual γ - δ -position of the double bond with respect to the carboxyl group (Winterstein and Hammerle, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1931, 199, 56, 64, 74; Haworth, *Ann. Report*, 1939, 338).

In the presence of an acidic catalyst, the methyl ester of indocentoic acid condensed with two molecules of acetone, forming a crystalline di-isopropylidene derivative. This indicates that all the four remaining oxygen functions in its molecule are in the form of hydroxyl groups. With pyridine and acetic anhydride and also with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, under usual conditions, indocentoic acid was converted into a diacetyl derivative, the remaining two hydroxyl groups being resistant towards acetylation. In this respect indocentoic acid differs from centoic acid and asiatic acid, both of which form triacetyl derivatives (Parts I and II, *loc. cit.*).

The presence of at least one primary hydroxyl group in indocentoic acid was indicated by the copper bronze test (Heywood and Kon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1125; Tsuda and Kitagawa, *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 1604). But as the acid contains only two acetylatable hydroxyl groups, one of which will be the usual secondary C₃-hydroxyl group, common for triterpenes, the remaining one must necessarily be the one and the only primary hydroxyl group present in its molecule, as primary hydroxyl groups occurring in triterpenes are usually acetylatable. This conclusion could be further confirmed from the information given below.

Indocentoic acid contains an α -glycol linkage as shown by the consumption of one molecule of sodium periodate. The same α -glycol linkage is also present in the methyl ester, diacetyl derivative and the diacetylated methyl ester. Both the resistant hydroxyl groups are therefore involved in the glycol linkage. The presence of glycol linkage in the diacetylated product further confirms the presence of four hydroxyl groups. The periodate scission product, obtained as above, gave tests for aldehyde. At least one of the hydroxyl groups involved in the α -glycol linkage is therefore a resistant secondary hydroxyl group, similar to that occurring in other triterpenes like sumaresinolic acid, echinocystic acid, quillaic acid, gelin A, manila diol etc. (Jegar, "Fort. der. Chim. Org. Naturstoffe", 1950, pp. 24, 31, 32, 33, 46). The other hydroxyl group involved in the α -glycol linkage must also necessarily be a tertiary or a secondary hydroxyl group, as the triterpene structure excludes the possibility of a resistant primary hydroxyl group taking part in the formation of an α -glycol linkage with another resistant secondary hydroxyl group, a conclusion which is also indicated as no formaldehyde is formed during oxidation. This finding further confirms the presence of only one primary hydroxyl group in indocentoic acid.

Dehydrogenation of indocentoic acid with selenium, carried out on a small scale, followed by chromatographic separation, indicates the usual dehydrogenation products.

From a critical interpretation of these results, it would appear that indocentoic acid is very similar to asiatic acid and centoic acid. It is isomeric with the latter (I) and may be expected to have the same basic α -amyrin skeleton.

In common with other triterpenes, indocentoic acid will also have an acetylatable secondary hydroxyl group at C₂. This group, however, could not be a component part of the α -glycol linkage, as that would have required the presence of another secondary acetylatable hydroxyl at C₃, similar to that present in asiatic acid (vide Part II, *loc. cit.*).

Irrespective of the position of the α -glycol linkage, composed of two non-acetylatable hydroxyl groups, the primary hydroxyl group present in the acid must be located on C₂₃ (or 24), as no other position of the same can explain the formation of the diisopropylidene derivative which will be formed only by α - and β -glycols. This leads to the partial structure (II) for indocentoic acid. If the α -glycol linkage is located at "C₆-C₇", as in the case of centoic acid (I), the two acids will have the same structural formulae, differing, probably, in steric disposition of the hydroxyl groups. Location of the α -glycol linkage in indocentoic acid, however, is still uncertain.

The water-soluble glycoside, indocentelloside, has also been preliminarily examined. On hydrolysis it furnished reducing sugars and a triterpenic aglycone which on characterisation through its brucine salts was found to be identical with indocentoic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Unless otherwise stated, samples were usually dried to a constant weight at 100°-110°/1-2 mm. Equivalent weights were determined following the standard micro procedure in dilute alcoholic solution and always checked by simultaneous determination of the same for cholic acid.

The plant was collected in Assam, dried in the sun and then shipped to Cambridge for examination. Nearly six months passed after collection, before its chemical examination could be commenced.

For the isolation of the salts, sugars, essential oils and pectin, the same procedure as described in Part I (*loc. cit.*) was employed.

Triterpenes and Glycosides.—These were isolated from the alcoholic extract of the plant. The process was the same as described in Part I (*loc. cit.*). The extract after drying was found to contain less of waxy material as compared to the former variety. After extraction with petrol and processing through lead acetate-treatment etc., a pale yellow alcoholic solution was obtained as a final product. On concentration and dilution with water, it deposited a mixture of triterpenic acids (160 g. from 9 kg. of the plant). The aqueous mother-liquor contained indocentelloside.

Separation of the Acids through Brucine Salt.—The dried triterpene acids (160 g.) and brucine (128 g.) were dissolved in alcohol (2½ litres) and refluxed (charcoal, 20 g.) for 2 hours. After filtration the solution was left at 0° for 24 hours. The crystals of brucine salt (120 g., large plates) were collected and washed with ice-cold alcohol (300 c.c.). The mother-liquor on concentration and cooling furnished a second crop

which on recrystallisation provided about 11 g. of brucine salt; the latter was added to the main crop. The combined amount after recrystallisation from alcohol three times afforded the brucine salt of indocentoic acid in the form of microscopically pure large plates, yield 60 g., $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, -77° (alcohol, $c = 1.37\%$).

For the isolation of the free acid, the brucine salt, as obtained above, was decomposed with mineral acid in the usual way, and the free acid was further purified by reprecipitation from alcohol and dried to a constant weight; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, $+38.6$ (pyridine, $c = 1.464\%$). In a preheated bath (22°), the acid melted at 272° , which was fairly reproducible. It developed a yellow colour with tetranitromethane and the usual cherry-red colour with $H_2SO_4-HNO_3$. (Found: C, 71.51; H, 9.82; equiv., 500.0, 497.0, 502.1. $C_{30}H_{48}O_6$ requires C, 71.39; H, 9.59 per cent. $Equiv.$, 504.68).

Estimation of Glycol-linkage.—The same procedure as in the case of centoic acid was followed. Periodate consumed was 1.067 mole (calc. 1.0 mole). The scission product responded to various tests for aldehyde.

Diacetyl derivative.—Indocentoic acid (1 g.) was dissolved in anhydrous pyridine (15 c.c.) and acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) was added. The mixture was left at room temperature for 24 hours and then the acetyl derivative was isolated and worked up in the usual way. It could not be crystallised; it shrank at 145° and formed a glass at 150° . (Found: C, 69.40; H, 8.73; equiv., 591.6, 591.6, 590.2. $C_{34}H_{52}O_6$ requires C, 69.36; H, 8.90 per cent. $Equiv.$, 588.76).

The same acetyl derivative was obtained by refluxing indocentoic acid with acetic anhydride, glacial acetic acid and freshly fused sodium acetate for 3 hours and then working up the product. The derivative shrank at 140° and formed a glass at 150° . (Found: C, 69.20; H, 8.51. $C_{34}H_{52}O_6$ requires C, 69.36; H, 8.90 per cent). Both the diacetyl derivatives gave positive test with Feigl's periodate-silver nitrate test, indicating the presence of glycol linkage (Feigl, "Spot Tests", 1946, p. 327).

Methyl Ester of Indocentoic Acid.—To the powdered acid (5 g.), suspended in anhydrous ether (100 c.c.), a distilled solution of diazomethane was added in excess. Within a short time the entire amount of the acid went into solution. After a few hours at room temperature, the methyl ester started crystallising out, and after 24 hours the entire mass had crystallised; yield 4.5 g. It could be recrystallised from ether or acetone-methanol mixture, m.p. $173-75^\circ$. (Found: C, 72.75; H, 9.60. $C_{31}H_{50}O_6$ requires C, 71.78; H, 9.72 per cent). A better analysis for carbon could not be obtained. The ester showed characteristic periodate reaction for α -glycol. The scission product gave tests for the aldehyde function.

Di-isopropylidene-methyl Ester.—The crystalline methyl ester (1 g.) was dissolved by warming in acetone (10 c.c.); HCl (conc., 4 drops) was added and the mixture left at room temperature. Within a short time the isopropylidene derivative crystallised in fine needles. The crystals were collected (0.6 g.) after a few hours and recrystallised from 5 c.c. of acetone, m.p. 213° . (Found: C, 74.12; H, 10.0. $C_{37}H_{58}O_6$ requires C, 74.21; H, 9.76 per cent).

Bromolactone of Indocentoic Acid.—This preparation was examined only from the qualitative point. Following the same procedure as in the case of centoic acid, indocen-

toic acid (0.5 g.) gave about 0.3 g. of the neutral bromolactone containing bromine, as indicated by qualitative tests.

Detection of Primary Alcoholic Group.—Exactly the same procedure, as employed in the case of centoic acid in Part II (*loc. cit.*), was used. Formaldehyde formed during the reaction was characterised as its dimedone derivative, m.p. and mixed m.p. 189°.

Dehydrogenation of Indocentoic Acid.—The acid (5 g.) and selenium (6 g.) were used for the experiment. Initially the same procedure as in the case of centoic acid was used. The ethereal solution, obtained after extraction of the dehydrogenation product, was filtered and then by treatment with dilute alkali (2 × 25 c.c.) was divided into (i) phenolic fraction and (ii) non-phenolic fraction. The alkaline extract on acidification and extraction with ether gave the free phenol (4 mg.) which was qualitatively characterised through colour reaction with diazonium salt.

The non-phenolic portion after removal of the solvent was dissolved in benzene (10 c.c.) and chromatographed on a column of alumina (100 g., grade o). The column was developed with light petroleum-benzene. Five fractions were collected. Removal of solvents gave the corresponding products from :

- (i) 300 c.c. of 3 : 1 petroleum-benzene ; 0.7 g. oil ; came out through the column very rapidly.
- (ii) 250 c.c. of 3 : 1 petroleum-benzene ; 60 mg., oil
- (iii) 250 c.c. of 2 : 1 do ; 100 mg., crystals
- (iv) 250 c.c. of 2 : 1 do ; 80 mg., oil and crystals
- (v) 1000 c.c. of benzene ; 100 mg., crystals.

Fractions (i) and (ii) formed a picrate which after three crystallisations from alcohol melted at 120° and it was possibly the picrate of 1:7-dimethylnaphthalene, m.p. 121°. Analysis also supported this. (Found: C, 56.32; H, 4.06. $C_{18}H_{16}O_7N_3$ requires C, 56.10; H, 3.92 per cent). Formation of 1:7-dimethylnaphthalene is possible from triterpenes. Sapotaline could not be isolated in quantity. The other fractions on crystallisations from benzene-petroleum, followed by micro-vacuum sublimation (bath temp. 260°/10⁻⁴ mm.) gave shining crystals, m.p. 298°. The melting and sublimation temperatures were comparable to those of 1:8-dimethylpicene (m.p. 305°, corr.) or 1:7:8-trimethylpicene (m.p. 309°, corr.).

Indocenteiloside.—The ultimate mother-liquor, obtained after removal of triterpene, was acidified and then saponified by refluxing for a short time. The acidic aglycone (4 g. from 1 kg. of the dried plant) was converted into brucine salt, which was purified by repeated crystallisations from alcohol in microscopically pure, large plates similar to that of centoic acid but having no sharp melting point. It started softening at 145 and then slowly melted into a glass; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, -70° (EtOH, $c = 1.3\%$) same as the brucine salt of indocentoic acid. Due to lack of any sharp melting point, identity through mixed melting point was not dependable; microscopic purity and optical rotation were to be preferred.

Other Miscellaneous Constituents.—The mother-liquor, left after the first crystallisation of the brucine salt of triterpenic acid mixture, was processed partly according to the triangular scheme with the following broad results :

(i) Amorphous brucine salt (about 40 g.). The free acid from it formed a crystalline potassium salt and could be purified through that derivative. The acid, thus obtained, formed a crystalline brucine salt.

(ii) A dark mother-liquor, containing a considerable amount of highly soluble brucine salt, somewhat similar to that of centellic acid.

(iii-iv) Two minor unspecified fractions. These fractions were not further examined.

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